

**Kinetics of Iodination of Naphthalene and
1-Methylnaphthalene in presence of
Nitric and Sulphuric Acids**

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GENERALLY, iodine does not react spontaneously with aromatic compounds other than phenols and amines. With other compounds, the reaction may be effected by the addition of an oxidising agent¹. The kinetics of iodination of a number of substituted benzenes by iodine and nitric acid in aqueous acetic acid medium have been investigated. Evidence shows that the iodinating species is I^+ , which reacts in a slow step with the aromatic compound. Direct iodination of aromatic compounds in the presence of a mixture of nitric and sulphuric acids has been investigated and the iodinating agent is formed with the participation of the nitronium cation².

Experimental

All the organic compounds used were of A.R. grade. Iodine (analaR) was used as such. Acetic acid (A.R.) was used after repeated purification.

Kinetics of the title reaction was followed by estimating the unreacted iodine iodimetrically with

sodium thiosulphate. Urea was added to the reaction mixture to suppress the action of nitric acid on NaI (otherwise, the nitric acid present in the reaction mixture liberates iodine from sodium iodide, which is formed during the titration between the unreacted iodine and sodium thiosulphate).

For both naphthalene and 1-methylnaphthalene, the stoichiometry is 1 : 1 and the product of this reaction is the iodo-compound of the starting material.

Results and Discussion

The nitrating mixture (nitric acid and sulphuric acid) produces NO_2^+ ion, which then reacts with I_2 to give I^+ , which may be the active species for iodination⁸.

The effect of varying [substrate] on the reaction rate reveals that an increase in [substrate] increases the reaction rate for both the substrates. The $k_1 \times 10^6$ values (s^{-1}) for the iodination of naphthalene under the experimental conditions adopted are 7.67, 9.36, 11.7, 13.6 and 19.2 for [naphthalene] $\times 10^2 M$ values of 2.0, 3.0, 4.0, 5.0 and 6.0 respectively. For 1-methylnaphthalene, the values of $k_1 \times 10^4$ (s^{-1}) are 3.89, 5.95, 7.08 and 9.74 at [1-methylnaphthalene] $\times 10^2 M$ values of 1.0, 2.0, 3.4 and 4.0 respectively. The plots of $\log k_1$ vs \log [substrate] were linear with unit slopes.

A set of reactions was carried out by varying the concentration of iodine and maintaining the other concentrations constant. The reaction is first order in iodine as is evident from the linear plots of $\log(a-x)$ vs time. The rate constants are almost the same confirming the first order dependence of the reaction on both the substrates.

Effect of varying acid concentration: Experiments were carried out separately by varying the concentrations of sulphuric acid and nitric acid. The rate was found to increase markedly for both the substrates on increasing the [acids]. The kinetic results reveal that one molecule of nitric acid reacts with two molecules of sulphuric acid to give the nitronium ion,

Since the NO_2^+ ion is likely to be present in the reaction mixture, the products were analysed for the presence of NO_2 group; however, no such products were found. This seems to confirm the suggestion that the NO_2^+ ion is used in the formation of the iodinating agent I^+ and not for nitration. When other mineral acids were used (phosphoric or perchloric) in place of sulphuric acid, direct iodination did not occur.

The rate increases on increasing the percentage of acetic acid in the medium. The linear plot $\log k_1$ vs $1/D$ indicates that there is a reaction between an ion and a dipolar molecule⁴. This is supported by the effect of added anion such as SO_4^{2-} on the

reaction rate; the change in rate constants is negligible for both the substrates.

Thermodynamic parameters: The Arrhenius parameters have been computed. There is a slight difference in ΔG^\ddagger values for naphthalene and 1-methylnaphthalene (85.4 and 81.2 kJ mol^{-1}) indicating that the latter is iodinated more easily than the former. Probably, this is due to the presence of CH_3 in the substrate which accelerates the electrophilic reaction. No large difference is observed in ΔH^\ddagger (50.1 and 71.9 kJ mol^{-1}) and also ΔG^\ddagger values, because the H in naphthalene is replaced by CH_3 group in 1-methylnaphthalene, which may not alter the mechanism of iodination. The negative ΔS^\ddagger values (-113 and $-99 \text{ JK}^{-1} \text{ mol}^{-1}$) indicate the formation of a bulky transition state. The E_a values are 52.7 and 74.5 kJ mol^{-1} for naphthalene and 1-methylnaphthalene respectively.

Mechanism: The mixture of nitric acid and sulphuric acid gives rise to NO_2^+ ion, which then reacts with iodine to produce I^+ . Therefore, I^+ may be the active iodinating species in the present study. The rate-determining step is likely to involve an interaction between I^+ and the substrate molecule leading to the transition state. This mechanism is depicted as follows:

The rate law is as follows:

$$\text{Rate} = k[\text{substrate}][\text{I}^+]$$

$$[\text{I}^+] = \frac{K_2[\text{NO}_2^+][\text{I}_2]}{[\text{NO}_2\text{I}]}$$

$$[\text{NO}_2^+] = \frac{K_1[\text{HNO}_3][\text{H}_2\text{SO}_4]^2}{[\text{HSO}_4^-][\text{H}_3\text{O}^+]}$$

$$[\text{I}^+] = \frac{K_1 K_2 [\text{HNO}_3][\text{H}_2\text{SO}_4]^2 [\text{I}_2]}{[\text{HSO}_4^-][\text{H}_3\text{O}^+][\text{NO}_2\text{I}]}$$

Therefore,

$$\text{Rate} = \frac{k K_1 K_2 [\text{HNO}_3][\text{H}_2\text{SO}_4]^2 [\text{I}_2][\text{Substrate}]}{[\text{HSO}_4^-][\text{H}_3\text{O}^+][\text{NO}_2\text{I}]}$$

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